

Satisfaction Level of Central Districts' Citizens of Nueva Vizcaya on Police-Community Relations Programs of the Philippine National Police

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Abstract

This study evaluated citizen satisfaction with the Philippine National Police (PNP) Police-Community Relations (PCR) programs in the municipalities of Solano, Bayombong, and Bambang in Nueva Vizcaya. The objective was to determine the overall satisfaction levels and identify the factors influencing satisfaction across four PCR program categories: Public Information, Public Relations, Civic Action, and Psychological Programs. A quantitative research approach was used through a descriptive-comparative method, involving a structured survey and statistical analyses, including descriptive statistics (median, standard deviation) and comparative tests (t-test, ANOVA). A total of 585 registered voters, purposively sampled from the three municipalities' Local Government Units (LGUs), participated in the study. Satisfaction was measured using a 5-point Likert scale. Findings revealed consistently high overall satisfaction, with average ratings exceeding 4.2 across all program categories. Among these, Public Information programs garnered the highest satisfaction. Significant differences emerged based on demographic factors: male respondents reported higher satisfaction than females; older participants expressed greater satisfaction than younger ones; and residents of Bambang indicated the highest satisfaction among the three areas. These results suggest generally positive perceptions of the PNP's PCR programs while also emphasizing areas for improvement. The PNP should consider tailoring PCR strategies to specific demographic segments to enhance overall program effectiveness further. Improving communication efforts, particularly in Solano and Bayombong, and reinforcing community partnerships are essential. Regular program evaluations and the replication of successful initiatives will help sustain and improve program impact. Lastly, further research is strongly recommended to explore the underlying causes of demographic variations in satisfaction and support for evidence-based improvements.

Keywords: Civic action, community, police-community relations, psychological programs, public information, public relations

Introduction

Police-Community Relations (PCR) programs have contributed significantly to society. They aim to improve the interactions between law enforcement agencies and the communities they serve. It builds trust and cooperation among people from the community. With trust, Police-Community Relations (PCR) programs become more efficient since the community is cooperative with the programs. Built police-community relationships helps reduce crime rates because the trust that the community gives plays a major role in making this happen.

This study assessed the satisfaction level of the citizens of the central districts on police-community relations (PCR) programs of the Philippine National Police (PNP). Knowing the satisfaction level, this study may guide how the Philippine National Police will effectively implement Police-Community Relations (PCR) programs. Meanwhile, this study may serve as a basis for future researchers to use as a basis for future works to arise and for police officers to use as a guide in considering the public for future Police-Community Relations (PCR) Programs. The paper only focused on examining the level of satisfaction of the citizens of the central districts of Nueva Vizcaya.

Police-Community Relations

The public and the police enjoy an ambivalent relationship with each other in that they reciprocate equivocal attitudes mixed with fear and respect (Whitaker, 2023). For the police and the public to work, both parties should engage and communicate as to what should be done to address certain issues in the community. The importance of mutual respect between the police and the public is that they establish strong and trusted relations that make it efficient in making society safe and protected. Police are defined as the department of government concerned primarily with the maintenance of public order, safety, and health; they also enforce laws and possess executive, judicial, and legislative powers (Merriam Webster, 2024). Its goal is to enforce the law, maintain peace and order in the community, and ensure public safety.

Republic Act No. 8551 states that the Philippine National Police (PNP) shall be a community and service-oriented agency responsible for maintaining peace and order and public safety. It will be structured to guarantee accountability and integrity in police discretion while enhancing the efficiency and effectiveness of its members and units in carrying out their duties. With that, the Directorate of Police Community Relations (DCPR) formulates police community (PCR) plans, programs, and policies geared towards enhancing community and citizen participation in support of the operational plans of the Philippine National Police. Its goal is to restore public trust and confidence in the PNP and improve community participation and inter-agency coordination through police activities. It also aims to change public perception and improve their opinions and views towards the PNP. In the same year, Brig. Gen. Jose Melencio Nartatez Jr., National Capital Region Police Office (NCRPO) chief, stressed that the police officers are the contact persons of the society. "If the people can't contact us, they will call the enemy" (Nartatez, 2023). Such remarks highlighted not only the role of the police regarding effective law enforcement but also the role of the citizens. This remark implies the importance of police-community relations.

As stated in Republic Act 6975, as amended by Republic Act 8551, the restructuring and renaming of the Police Community Relations Group (PCRG) to the Police Community Affairs and Development Group (PCADG) in the Philippines marks a significant pivot towards enhancing the Philippine National Police's (PNP) engagement and interaction with the communities it serves. This strategic move, as outlined in the detailed provisions, aims to not only bolster the police's capability to maintain peace and order but also to deepen the roots of trust between the police force and the civilian population. By placing the PCADG under the functional authority of the Director for Police Community Relations (DPCR), the initiative underscores a centralized yet community-focused approach to law enforcement and public safety. The creation of the Police Community Affairs and Development Group (PCADG), as mandated by the PNP's higher echelons, signifies a pivotal shift towards a more community-centric policing model. It embodies an acknowledgment of the critical role that community engagement and development play in ensuring public safety and peace. As these initiatives unfold, they have the potential to transform the landscape of policing in the Philippines, making it more responsive, inclusive, and effective in addressing the needs and concerns of the Filipino people.

Challenges to Police-Community Relations Programs

Community policing is essential to fostering strong police-community relations and addressing local issues. Building a solid partnership with the community begins with the police establishing a strong connection with neighborhood residents. Police should actively engage the community in efforts to reduce crime. Problem-solving is key to identifying both the concerns and

potential solutions within the neighborhood. Police-Community Relation Programs can only occur through the help of the community for community involvement because, without the trust and involvement of the community, any attempts at Police-Community Relation Programs will fail.

In the study conducted by Corpuz (2023), the police assistance during the Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic was satisfactory. Police officers took adequate precautions that aligned with the Philippine government's basic health protocols, showing careful conduct during interactions to minimize the risk of virus transmission. Even with limited resources, they showed adaptability in protecting themselves. Public cooperation also played a key role in effectively implementing pandemic-related measures.

Meanwhile, the study of Cimene et al. (2022) says that the independent community satisfaction survey suggests that the PNP's community engagement initiatives are positively received by the public, particularly in terms of how the community perceives safety, security, respect for, and trust in the police force. Prenzler and Porter (2015), in their study, *"Improving police behavior and police-community relations through innovative responses to complaints,"* talked about how important it is for police to have a good system to handle complaints. They say this system helps make sure police are held accountable, gives a voice to people affected by police actions, and deals with wrong behavior. They look into how complaints are usually handled, find problems with the old ways, and suggest new ideas like setting up independent groups to check complaints, solving issues informally, and catching problems early to improve trust between police and the community.

The impact of police violence on the public's overall attitude toward interpersonal violence must be considered (DeVylder et al., 2020). It can affect and influence a person's societal norms and discernment. If violence is perceived as justifiable, it may influence public attitudes towards other forms of violence. Police violence will shatter trust in law enforcement and the justice system. Since the launch of former President Rodrigo Duterte's "war on drugs" in 2016, police have been associated with numerous extrajudicial killings during anti-drug operations. These controversial cases involve thousands of deaths carried out by law enforcement and armed individuals linked to authorities. In light of these concerns, it is essential to strengthen the relationship between the police and the community for the greater good. According to Jackson (2015), "In approaching the fundamental shortfalls in trust between law enforcement and the community, that exist in the country, there is a clear federal role and, therefore, actions that can be taken to support it." DILG of Region 2 conducted a program entitled "MASA MASID" (Mamamayang Ayaw sa Anomalya, Mamamayang Ayaw sa Ilegal na Droga) Program which promotes community involvement wherein they influence people to support and help in addressing problems in the society like corruption, illegal drugs, criminality and other threats to the people living in the community.

Understanding why people complain is key to using complaints to solve deeper problems and help police and communities get along better. A study by Prenzler et al. (2013) found that most people in Queensland, Australia, and Britain want independent groups to investigate serious complaints like assault and bribery. When it comes to how happy people are with the complaint process, many are unhappy with how the police handle complaints. In a journal written by Mbewu et al. (2020), it is found that Police are not very supportive of the victims of crime and that citizens would like to remain anonymous when reporting an incident. The police are also most likely not to do a follow-up investigation when people report a crime. Given these circumstances, the community expresses their distrust of law enforcement, fear of retaliation, and their perceived ineffectiveness of the police.

Prenzler et al. (2013) found that about 70% were not satisfied when the police managed the process. However, 77% of people who had their complaints looked into by independent groups were happier with that process. The Police Ombudsman for Northern Ireland, an independent group, showed higher satisfaction levels, suggesting that outside oversight works better for resolving complaints. The study examined how well different ways of solving complaints worked, including when an outside party helps mediate. In the US, people were much happier with this independent mediation compared to when the police tried to solve complaints themselves.

Status of Police-Community Relation Programs in Nueva Vizcaya

Police-community relations have always been visible in the different parts of Nueva Vizcaya. In an article from PS Balita, in December 2023, the Nueva Vizcaya Women in the Police Service Organization (NVWPSO) conducted a Gift Giving Activity and Campaign to End Violence Against Women (VAW) for Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDL) of the Bureau of Jail and Management Penology in Brgy. Curifang, Solano, Nueva Vizcaya was led by Police Lieutenant Colonel Angeline Amangan, Adviser of NVWPSO. The activity aimed to raise awareness about Violence Against Women and provide support to the community. The said activity raised awareness to end violence against women. In another article, the 2nd Nueva Vizcaya Provincial Mobile Force Company conducted Operation B.E.S. (Bisita Eskwela "I am Strong") held at Dupax Del Norte National High School, Brgy. Malasin, Dupax Del Norte, Nueva Vizcaya on February 20, 2023. The said operation's goal was to further strengthen the knowledge of our youth. The PNP has conducted many police-community relations programs to influence the youth, protect women and children, and help the community.

Situated at the core of the Cagayan Valley in the Philippines, Nueva Vizcaya has achieved a significant turning point in its history. The province has been declared free from insurgency, a milestone that signals the conclusion of a challenging era and ushers in a new phase of peace, stability, and economic prosperity. This accomplishment is the result of collective efforts from the military, local government entities, and the broader community, aiming to overcome the adversities brought about by insurgency. This new status is expected to have profound effects on economic growth, security, and the quality of life for the people of Nueva Vizcaya.

The official announcement of Nueva Vizcaya as an insurgency-free area signifies a crucial chapter in the province's narrative, heralding a period of peace and economic opportunity. Major General Audrey Pasia, leading the 5th Infantry Division, announced during a provincial capitol flag-raising event, emphasizing the region's move towards normalized and stable security conditions (Ebreo, 2024). The province met all necessary benchmarks through various phases, from dealing with insurgency to achieving stable internal peace and security. Governor Jose Gambito of Nueva Vizcaya has expressed optimism regarding the economic prospects and investment opportunities that this peace and security assurance brings. This achievement is the culmination of persistent anti-insurgency operations by the Armed Forces of the Philippines (AFP) and the Philippine National Police since 1997, supported by a resolution from the Sangguniang Panlalawigan and endorsements from several provincial councils, as well as certifications from the Peace Law Enforcement and Development Support and the National Task Force to End Local Communist Armed Conflict (Ebreo, 2024).

Success Rates/ Stories of Police-Community Relations in Other Places

Community policing represents a significant shift in law enforcement philosophy, prioritizing collaboration, communication, and proactive problem-solving between police officers and the communities they serve (Menon, 2023). This approach aims to foster mutual trust, address the

underlying causes of crime, and ultimately build safer communities through shared responsibility. Case studies from around the world showcase the effectiveness of community policing strategies in reducing crime and strengthening police-community relations.

The city of Chicago responded decisively to the surging crime rates of the early 1990s by embarking on the planning stages of a pioneering community-policing program in 1991. This initiative was launched against the backdrop of an alarming spike in various crimes, including assaults, robberies, and gang-related violence. Particularly noteworthy was the eruption of a full-scale drug war on the South Side in August 1991, which marked a harrowing chapter in the city's history, recording one of the highest murder rates on record. Moreover, 1992 saw a peak in homicides, with gang-related killings reaching unprecedented levels, underscored by a shift in the weaponry utilized on the streets, as automatic and semiautomatic firearms became increasingly prevalent, amplifying the lethality of confrontations.

Amidst this backdrop of escalating violence and growing public concern, the pressure mounted on city officials to devise effective strategies to combat crime and ensure public safety. The urgent imperative to address the crisis prompted a search for innovative approaches capable of addressing the root causes of criminal activity. Consequently, the exploration of community policing emerged as a promising avenue for fostering closer collaboration between law enforcement agencies and local communities. By prioritizing community engagement and proactive problem-solving, this approach sought to empower residents to actively contribute to crime prevention efforts, thereby cultivating a sense of ownership and shared responsibility for public safety.

Recognizing the need for swift and comprehensive action, Chicago's leadership embarked on a trajectory aimed at redefining the relationship between law enforcement and the communities they serve. The adoption of community policing represented a strategic shift towards a more proactive and community-centered approach to law enforcement. By leveraging partnerships with residents and community organizations, the city aimed to establish a collaborative framework for addressing crime and social disorder, focusing on tailored interventions and preventive measures tailored to each neighborhood's unique needs and challenges.

Community policing has demonstrated its effectiveness internationally, even in challenging environments. In Nairobi's Kibera slum, for instance, a collaboration between local law enforcement and the Shining Hope for Communities organization resulted in the establishment of a reporting system for gender-based violence. This initiative empowered women and enhanced community safety by providing a platform for addressing such critical issues (Menon, 2023). Similarly, the Glasgow Violence Reduction Unit in Scotland successfully implemented community policing strategies to tackle gang violence, leading to a notable reduction in violent crimes through early intervention and active engagement with the community (Menon, 2023).

In the Philippine context, amidst the global challenges facing law enforcement agencies, the Philippine National Police (PNP) distinguishes itself through proactive and community-oriented initiatives. Directing attention from international dynamics to local concerns, the PNP's efforts highlight a steadfast commitment to addressing domestic needs and upholding public safety. Through diverse programs and initiatives, the PNP demonstrates a resolute dedication to serving and protecting Filipino communities, setting a standard for effective law enforcement nationwide.

The effectiveness of community policing is evident through initiatives like the Community Affairs Program (CAP) implemented by the Police Community Relations (PCR) in various

municipalities. The CAP focuses on mobilizing communities for crime prevention and overall security, facilitating collaboration between law enforcement agencies and residents. Through activities such as seminars, meetings, and the establishment of police assistance stations, police engage with community members to address concerns and devise customized solutions to local crime and safety challenges. For example, according to Tondo et al. (2020), in Zamboanga del Sur, the PNP and Barangay officials perceived that the extent of community-oriented policing in Dumingag was implemented without lapses. Crime rates have decreased over the past five years since the policy was implemented. The amount or frequency of crimes occurring has decreased in the last five years after the policy was implemented. It suggests a positive outcome of the policy in reducing criminal activity over that period.

Within the intricate dynamics of society, the relationship between law enforcement agencies and the communities they serve plays a pivotal role. This connection, often referred to as police-community relations, serves as the foundation for maintaining public safety, fostering trust, and instilling a sense of security among citizens. Amidst this framework, stories of remarkable valor and selflessness, such as that of Police Senior Master Sergeant Jason Magno, serve as symbols of hope and inspiration, guiding the way towards stronger and more harmonious police-community relations (Talabong, 2019). The aftermath of Magno's heroic deed resonated not only within the community he served but also deeply within the ranks of the Philippine National Police (PNP). In this regard, the PNP's decision to posthumously consider Magno for the highest honor, the *Medalya ng Kadakilaan* (PNP Heroism Medal), underscores the recognition of his exceptional bravery and unwavering commitment to public service. Furthermore, the acknowledgment of Magno's colleague, Senior Master Sergeant Alice Balido, who also responded to the incident with valor, further highlights the collective spirit of courage and sacrifice prevailing within the law enforcement community.

In the words of Lieutenant General Archie Gamboa, the officer-in-charge of the PNP, Magno's ultimate sacrifice "gave new meaning to the undying line in the PNP Hymn 'ihandog ang iisang buhay,' symbolizing the profound impact of his actions on the collective consciousness of the nation. This sentiment encapsulates the idea that Magno, along with numerous other police heroes preceding him, embodies the spirit of patriotism and selflessness akin to that of the nation's revered national heroes (Talabong, 2019). The 28th Police Community Relations (PCR) Month commenced at Camp Bagong Diwa, Taguig City, on July 3, 2023, as reported by Alice Sicat in a Philippine Information Agency (PIA) article titled "NCRPO hosts 28th Police Community Relations Month kick-off event." This event highlighted the strong partnership between the community and the Philippine National Police (PNP), with various advocacy groups and stakeholders participating (Sicat, 2023).

With the theme "Serbisyong Nagkakaisa para sa Ligtas at Maunlad na Pamayanan" (United Service for a Safe and Progressive Community), PCR Month aims to emphasize community engagement, a key agenda of NCRPO Chief Police Major General Edgar Allan Okubo. The event underscored the significance of community-oriented policies to achieve the PNP's mission of maintaining peace, order, and public safety, aligning with the Revitalize Pulis sa Barangay Program led by Maj. Gen. Okubo, thus reinforcing the importance of collaborative efforts between law enforcement and local communities.

Effective police-community relations are essential for maintaining public safety. This study provides insights into how police interactions impact perceptions of safety within communities, thus contributing to a safer environment for all residents. Additionally, assessing satisfaction levels also provides valuable feedback on the effectiveness of current policing strategies and practices, enabling policymakers and law enforcement agencies to tailor interventions to address specific needs and concerns. Effective police-community relations are essential for maintaining public safety. Through

this study, insights can be gained into how police interactions impact perceptions of safety within communities, thus contributing to a safer environment for all residents. Additionally, assessing satisfaction levels also provides valuable feedback on the effectiveness of current policing strategies and practices, enabling policymakers and law enforcement agencies to tailor interventions to address specific needs and concerns.

Problems Encountered in the Police-Community Relations Implemented Program

A pivotal flaw in many community outreach programs is the absence of direct input from community members themselves, an issue highlighted by (NeoGov, 2023). Such programs often fail because they are shaped based on the agency's assumptions about community needs rather than through engagement with community leaders and members to understand their actual desires and requirements. This top-down approach can lead to initiatives that fail to address the real needs and priorities of the communities they aim to serve. Furthermore, the effectiveness of a community outreach program is significantly compromised when it does not reflect the community's diversity. (NeoGov, 2023) underscores the importance of inclusivity in outreach efforts, noting that they must embrace and include individuals from all racial, ethnic, cultural, and socioeconomic backgrounds. This diversity is essential, as different groups may have unique experiences and perceptions of local law enforcement, necessitating tailored approaches to engagement and support.

Moreover, the need for adequate training of police officers in community outreach skills is another critical point raised by NeoGov (2023). Officers tasked with engaging the community must be well-versed in communication, conflict resolution, and understanding cultural and racial diversity. Without this training, officers may struggle to connect with community members effectively, which is detrimental to the development of positive relationships and trust. This training should also extend to methods for compassionate and effective interactions with individuals facing mental health challenges, disabilities, or substance abuse issues. Additionally, NeoGov emphasizes the significance of consistency in community outreach programs (2023). A sporadic or short-term initiative fails to build trust and positive rapport with the community. Ongoing engagement is essential for fostering a lasting and positive.

Lastly, the absence of a robust follow-up and evaluation mechanism significantly impacts the ability to measure the success and effectiveness of community outreach efforts, as noted (NeoGov, 2023). Regular evaluations are essential to determine whether initiatives are effectively contributing to positive outcomes or if adjustments are necessary. Just as law enforcement agencies assess their reactive crime-fighting strategies, proactive community outreach efforts should undergo scrutiny to ensure they achieve their goals and genuinely benefit the community.

Additionally, socioeconomic issues like poverty, inequality, and restricted access to justice worsen the challenges of building strong police-community relationships in the Philippines. Communities grappling with systemic issues of marginalization and social exclusion frequently experience strained interactions with law enforcement agencies. To foster more inclusive and participatory approaches to community policing, it is imperative to address these underlying social and economic disparities. By giving marginalized communities more power and addressing the underlying causes of tension, we can build stronger, cooperative relationships between residents and law enforcement. This approach strengthens efforts to reduce crime and enhance public safety. Alarming incidents of brutality and abuse of power underscore the deteriorating trust between the Philippine police force and local communities. According to witness testimonies, instances like the one where a handcuffed individual, Arnaiz, was allegedly shot by police officers despite pleading for

surrender highlight the pervasive lack of respect for human rights within law enforcement (Al Jazeera, 2023). Such egregious acts not only erode public confidence in the police but also foster fear and distrust among community members, hindering any efforts to establish meaningful police-community relations. Moreover, the persistence of extrajudicial killings and ongoing reports of police violence perpetuates a cycle of impunity and injustice.

Human rights groups consistently raise concerns over the unchecked brutality and the failure of authorities to hold perpetrators accountable for their actions (Al Jazeera, 2023). This systemic failure to address police misconduct not only deepens societal divisions but also reinforces the perception of law enforcement as agents of oppression rather than guardians of public safety. As a result, efforts to foster positive police-community relations face significant challenges in the Philippines. Despite international scrutiny and calls for reform, the continuation of such abuses underscores the urgent need for comprehensive structural changes within law enforcement agencies to prioritize accountability, respect for human rights, and genuine engagement with local communities (Al Jazeera, 2023). Without meaningful reforms and redress for victims of police violence, building trust and cooperation between the police and the public will remain an elusive goal, perpetuating a cycle of fear, resentment, and discord. Prevalent obstacles in nurturing positive police-community relations in the Philippines.

Primarily, there exists a notable absence of accountability mechanisms within the law enforcement system, as evidenced by instances where allegations of infractions remain unaddressed, and wrongdoers evade justice. This atmosphere of impunity fosters a pervasive sense of fear and helplessness among victims, perpetuating a culture of silence that facilitates the unchecked escalation of power abuses (Gonzalez, 2020). Additionally, concerns persist regarding the excessive use of force by the Philippine National Police (PNP), a trend supported by the PNP's own data, which reveals a significant number of reported killings. This disproportionate reliance on force not only undermines the foundational principles of the rule of law but also fosters a perception of law enforcement as synonymous with violence, eroding trust and cohesion within communities (Gonzalez, 2020). Moreover, the series of targeted killings, including those of human rights advocates, journalists, legal professionals, and medical practitioners, perpetrated both by law enforcement and unidentified assailants, exacerbates the security landscape and impedes societal progress. These deliberate attacks not only pose direct threats to individual lives but also destabilize broader societal structures, hindering collective efforts toward stability and development. Addressing these multifaceted challenges necessitates a concerted approach that strengthens domestic accountability mechanisms, fosters robust cooperation between the Philippines and the United Nations, and cultivates a policing ethos prioritizing citizen protection, particularly for the most vulnerable members of society (Gonzalez, 2020).

The implementation of police-community relations in the Philippines faces significant challenges, as highlighted by critics and human rights groups. These stakeholders express skepticism towards the government's approach of swiftly cleansing the Philippine National Police (PNP) of corruption. Instead of thoroughly investigating alleged involvement in illegal activities and filing appropriate charges, the government's method of calling for "courtesy resignations" is seen as providing an easy exit for rogue cops (Asia Pacific Foundation of Canada, 2023). This shortcut approach undermines accountability and may hinder efforts to build trust between law enforcement and the community. Moreover, the policy's critics argue that it unfairly allows corrupt officers to evade proper scrutiny and consequences for their actions. Human rights watchdogs specifically point out that the directive to resign without thorough investigation provides an off-ramp for crooked

officers, bypassing the necessary steps of accountability (Asia Pacific Foundation of Canada, 2023). Such shortcuts not only undermine the rule of law but also risk perpetuating a culture of impunity within the police force, further eroding public trust in law enforcement agencies.

In light of these challenges, it becomes evident that a more comprehensive and transparent approach is needed to address corruption within the Philippine National Police while strengthening police-community relations. Rather than relying on expedient measures that may compromise accountability, there is a pressing need for thorough investigations and due process to hold errant officers accountable for their actions (Asia Pacific Foundation of Canada, 2023). Only through such measures can trust be restored between law enforcement and the communities they serve, fostering a safer and more just society for all Filipinos.

With that, this research will serve as a basis for the Philippine National Police to use as a reference to improve and enhance the established Police-Community Relations Programs (PCR) to enable the community to benefit from the police programs.

Statement of the Problem

The study sought to determine the level of satisfaction of citizens in the central districts of Nueva Vizcaya with the activities of police officers involved in police-community relation programs. Specifically, it examined their satisfaction in terms of public information programs, public relation programs, civic action programs, and psychological programs. Additionally, the study investigated whether there were significant differences in the respondents' levels of satisfaction with the police-community relation programs of the Philippine National Police when grouped according to profile variables such as sex, age, municipality, and participation in police-community relations programs.

Methodology

The study employed a quantitative research design, using both descriptive and comparative methods to measure citizen satisfaction with Police-Community Relations (PCR) programs in the central districts of Nueva Vizcaya. It aimed to assess satisfaction levels and explore variations among respondents based on demographic factors. Data collection was conducted through structured survey questionnaires, specifically designed to capture both demographic information and satisfaction ratings across four key PCR program areas: public information, public relations, civic action, and psychological programs.

The research locale included three central municipalities of Nueva Vizcaya—Solano, Bayombong, and Bambang—chosen for their diverse economic, cultural, and political significance. A total of 585 respondents (195 from each municipality) participated in the survey. The sample was selected using purposive sampling, focusing on residents aged 18 and above who had prior engagement with police-community programs. Slovin's formula was used to determine the sample size, applying a 5% margin of error and a 95% confidence level.

Survey questionnaires were administered in Filipino to ensure accessibility and understanding. The researchers personally visited the local government units (LGUs) of each municipality to seek permission and distribute surveys. The data gathering process involved strict ethical considerations, including obtaining informed consent from participants. Respondents were informed of the study's objectives, assured of confidentiality, and made aware that participation was entirely voluntary.

The completed surveys were collected, organized, and encoded in a spreadsheet for analysis. A designated statistical analyst conducted the data analysis. Throughout the data collection process, health and safety protocols were observed, and respondents were supported by the researchers on-site to ensure proper completion of the surveys. The systematic approach aimed to ensure the reliability, validity, and ethical integrity of the research process.

Ethical Considerations

To protect respondent confidentiality, researchers and their adviser securely disposed of used questionnaires to prevent public exposure of demographic information. This study received ethical approval from Saint Mary's University Research Ethics Board (SMU-REB), A218, Second Floor, Fr. Godfrey Lambrecht Building, SMU Main Campus, Ponce Street, Don Mariano Marcos, Bayombong, 3700 Nueva Vizcaya, Philippines.

Results and Discussion

Section 1. Level of Satisfaction of Citizens in the Central Districts of Nueva Vizcaya with the Activities of Police Officers in Police-Community Relation Programs

Public Information Programs

Citizens in central districts of Nueva Vizcaya are highly satisfied with Police-led Public Information Programs, with an overall mean score of 4.30 (SD = 0.75), indicating consistently positive feedback. All twelve evaluated items scored between 4.23 and 4.38, falling within the "Very Satisfied" range on the 5-point Likert scale. These results reflect strong community approval of the police's efforts to inform and engage the public through brochures, seminars, partnerships, and public events. The highest-rated initiative was the conduct of educational and historical lectures (M = 4.38), underscoring their value in community engagement.

The findings suggest that the police are successfully fostering trust and public awareness through effective information and outreach efforts. The consistently high ratings (mean scores from 4.23 to 4.38) suggest that citizens are highly satisfied with the police's public information programs. This finding indicates that police efforts to inform and engage the community through lectures, seminars, and printed materials are effective and well-received. Programs related to education, crime prevention, and community cleanliness appear especially impactful. Overall, the data shows that these initiatives are helping to strengthen public awareness, trust, and collaboration with law enforcement.

In a similar study conducted by Cimene et al. (2022) concluded that the community holds a positive view of the PNP's projects, programs, and activities aimed at community involvement. This is particularly evident in the favorable perceptions regarding safety and security, as well as the respect for and trust in PNP Region X. These results indicate that the police are effectively upholding their commitment to serve and protect the community.

Public Relation Program

People in the central districts of Nueva Vizcaya are very satisfied with how police officers run the Public Relations Program as part of their work with the community. The overall average score of 4.27 shows a strong and positive view of the program. The findings suggest that the consistently high scores reflect strong public confidence and approval of the agency's efforts in public relations.

Effective communication builds public awareness and transparency, especially via social media, contributing to trust.

In a similar study, Lacerna (2018) found that the majority of respondents were aware and moderately knowledgeable, with a generally positive attitude toward the information dissemination tools used by the Philippine National Police – Police Community Relations Group (PNP-PCRG) in Barangay Bagong Silang, Caloocan City. This suggests that the PNP-PCRG's tools are effective in disseminating information to the public, contributing to a more informed and organized community.

Civic Action Program

Citizens in the central districts of Nueva Vizcaya are very satisfied with police involvement in Civic Action Programs as part of their community relations work. The overall average score of 4.33, with a standard deviation of 0.75, places the results in the “Very Satisfied” category. All seven activities such as helping in blood donation drives, organizing medical and dental missions, deworming, environmental programs, youth sports, disaster response, and seminars for men—received high scores ranging from 4.27 to 4.41, showing strong satisfaction across all areas. The most highly rated activity was supporting blood donation campaigns with the Philippine Red Cross (M = 4.41), reflecting strong public approval for health-related police efforts. The lowest-rated, though still positive, was conducting seminars for men to discourage unproductive behavior (M = 4.27), which may suggest a need for slight improvement or better promotion.

This shows that the civic action program is well-received by the community. All components are considered important, particularly those involving healthcare, disaster response, and youth development. The feedback indicates a strong foundation for future civic engagement, with an opportunity to refine and expand specific initiatives to enhance overall impact. The findings of the study are similar to the study conducted by Pensotes Jr. and Bactol (2024), which was conducted in the Samar 2nd District and found that most participants were between 41 and 50 years old. This age group gave the highest overall ratings in terms of respect, trust, and satisfaction toward the PNP's community relations programs. The findings indicate that older individuals tend to show greater support for and appreciation of the PNP's efforts.

Psychological Program

Data shows how satisfied citizens in the central districts of Nueva Vizcaya are with the Psychological Programs carried out by the police as part of their community relations work. The overall average score is 4.36, with a standard deviation of 0.73, which means the public is “Very Satisfied.” All six program activities scored between 4.31 and 4.41, showing consistently high satisfaction. This suggests that the community appreciates the police's efforts to promote mental well-being, values education, and civic responsibility. The highest-rated activity was promoting seminars for barangay leaders about community relations (M = 4.41), showing that people value efforts that strengthen cooperation between leaders and the public.

This also suggests that the psychological program is highly relevant and impactful, particularly in fostering leadership skills, civic awareness, and youth development. The community recognizes the value of training and educational seminars in shaping a well-functioning, empathetic, and law-abiding society. The consistently high satisfaction levels support the sustainability and further development of such programs. In a study by Bobong et al. (2023), wherein the researchers looked into the operational plans the Philippine National conducted in Ozamiz City. The study found

that the PNP's operational plans implemented across various establishments were highly effective and should be sustained to uphold peace and order, as well as to deter unlawful or harmful activities that may threaten individuals, property, and communities. Respondents consistently indicated that these operations were indeed effective.

Section 2. Significant Differences in the Respondents' Level of Satisfaction with the Police-Community Relation Programs of the Philippine National Police when grouped according to profile variables

This part shows the analysis of the collected data from the survey questionnaires on the significant differences in the level of satisfaction with the Police-Community Relation Programs when grouped according to sex, age, address, and participation in Police-Community Relations Programs.

Comparison of Level of Satisfaction of Central District Citizens When Grouped According to Sex

The results show a significant difference in how satisfied male and female respondents are with the Philippine National Police's (PNP) community programs. Men gave a higher average satisfaction score of 4.37 (with a standard deviation of 0.40), while women gave a slightly lower average of 4.25 (with a standard deviation of 0.44). A t-value of 3.066 and a p-value of 0.002 confirm that this difference is statistically significant at the 0.05 level.

These results indicate that men are noticeably more satisfied with the PNP's community programs than women. These findings suggest that men and women may have different experiences or views and that the PNP should consider gender-sensitive approaches when planning and running these programs. In a study conducted by Villarín et al. (2018), no significant differences were found when results were analyzed by sex, age, and educational attainment. This implies that findings may vary depending on the location where Police-Community Relations Programs of the PNP are implemented.

Comparison of Level of Satisfaction of Central District Citizens When Grouped According to Age

The results show a significant difference in satisfaction with the Philippine National Police's (PNP) community programs based on age. Respondents aged 18 to 40 had an average satisfaction score of 4.27 (SD = 0.44), while those aged 40 to 60 had a higher average of 4.45 (SD = 0.32). The t-test result ($t = -4.238$, $df = 483$, $p < 0.001$) confirms that this difference is statistically significant. This means older respondents (ages 40–60) are noticeably more satisfied with the PNP's programs than younger ones (ages 18–40).

The findings suggest that age affects how people view these programs, with older individuals possibly having more positive experiences or a stronger appreciation for the initiatives. Older individuals tend to be more satisfied with the PNP's community initiatives than their younger counterparts. Basco-Galangco and Chinayo (2022) found that age plays a significant role in shaping public trust and satisfaction with the police. Their study revealed that younger individuals, particularly those aged 15–24 and 25–34, reported notably lower satisfaction compared to older age groups such as those aged 45–54 and 65 and above. The researchers also emphasized that trust in the police and satisfaction with their performance are distinct factors when evaluating police legitimacy.

Comparison of Level of Satisfaction of Central District citizens When Grouped According To Municipality

A. Post Hoc Comparisons - Municipality

The results of the one-way ANOVA show a significant difference in how satisfied people are with the PNP's police-community programs, depending on which municipality they live in. The analysis produced an F-value of 13.368 and a p-value of less than 0.001, indicating that the differences are statistically significant. This means a respondent's satisfaction may be influenced by their place of residence.

It shows that while overall program satisfaction is high, there are significant differences between municipalities, especially between Bambang and the other two. Bambang residents are significantly less satisfied, indicating a need for focused improvement efforts to ensure more equitable delivery of civic and psychological services across the Central District.

A related study by Araña et al. revealed that residents of Iligan City generally perceive their surroundings as safe and express moderate satisfaction with police services, especially in traffic management and support for victims. Despite this, only 40% reported satisfaction across all service areas, indicating room for improvement. The findings suggest that while some police efforts are effective, there is potential to strengthen weaker areas and build on existing strengths to improve community relations.

Comparison of the Level of Satisfaction of Central District citizens When Grouped According to Participation in Police-Community Relations Programs

A. Public Information Program

Across all four programs, participants reported significantly higher satisfaction than non-participants. The independent samples t-test results reveal a significant difference in satisfaction levels with the Philippine National Police's police-community relations programs based on respondents' participation. Participants consistently reported higher satisfaction than non-participants across all four program categories—Public Information, Public Relations, Civic Action, and Psychological Programs

Conclusion

The study concluded that citizens in the central districts of Nueva Vizcaya reported a high level of satisfaction with the Philippine National Police's (PNP) Police-Community Relations (PCR) programs. Respondents rated all four key areas—Public Information, Public Relations, Civic Action, and Psychological Programs—as highly satisfactory, with particular appreciation for initiatives such as educational lectures and social media updates, indicating strong community engagement and communication. However, the research also uncovered notable disparities in satisfaction based on gender, age, municipality, and prior program participation. Males, individuals aged 40 to 60, and residents of Bambang reported higher satisfaction levels compared to other groups. These findings suggest that while PCR programs are generally effective, tailored strategies may be necessary to address varying community needs and ensure more inclusive and balanced program outcomes.

Recommendations

Future researchers may incorporate qualitative approaches, such as interviews or focus group discussions with both citizens and police officers, to elaborate on and enrich the findings by uncovering underlying reasons for satisfaction or dissatisfaction. They may also consider including

additional profile variables such as educational attainment, occupation, income level, and length of residency in the municipality, for these may provide more detailed insights into how various segments of the population perceive police-community programs.

Other Recommendations:

The Philippine National Police (PNP) should strengthen its communication efforts by using localized and accessible platforms such as community radio, social media, and barangay forums. This will ensure that citizens are well-informed about ongoing police-community programs and foster greater trust and transparency.

The Philippine National Police should design and implement customized engagement strategies for different demographic groups. For instance, youth-oriented activities (e.g., school partnerships) and women-focused safety initiatives can help increase relevance and participation in Police-Community Relations Programs.

Future researchers could explore the reasons behind the lower satisfaction levels among female respondents and younger age groups.

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